

MIDA: A Multimodal Imaging-Based Model of the Human Head and Neck

Catalog of Regulatory Science Tools to Help Assess New Medical Devices

Technical Description

The MIDA model is a multimodal imaging-based detailed anatomical computer model of the human head and neck. The model offers detailed representation of brain surfaces, meninges, cerebrospinal fluid distribution, eyes, ears, and several deep brain structures, as well as many distinct muscles, bones and skull layers, blood vessels, cranial nerves, dental structures, and glands. Organs and tissues of the MIDA model are represented by three-dimensional, highly detailed computer-aided design (CAD) objects in standardized CAD data format. The individual CAD objects allow meshing at arbitrary resolutions without loss of small features. The MIDA model can be used in all software capable of importing and manipulating CAD data for the computational modelling in the device safety testing and design optimization.

The spatial resolution of the MIDA model is 500 μm isotropic. To enhance the visibility of specific tissues, the raw images were acquired using different magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) techniques:

- structural T1- and T2-weighted sequences
- a specific T2-weighted sequence with high nerve contrast optimized to enhance the structures of the ear and eye
- magnetic resonance angiography (MRA) to image the vasculature
- diffusion tensor imaging (DTI) to obtain information on tissue anisotropy and fiber orientation.

This model version includes a total of 116 structures (i.e., the 115 structures listed in Table 1 of Iacono *et al.* (2015) and the background [1]).

Intended Purpose

The MIDA model can be used for computational modeling studies involving anatomically correct models of the human anatomy, e.g., for electromagnetic simulations. Of particular interest are computational simulations to potentially investigate the safety and efficacy of medical devices in, on, or near the head. For example, the MIDA model was used in case-studies involving non-invasive neurostimulation, i.e., transcranial alternating current stimulation (tACS) [1], as well as invasive neurostimulation, i.e., deep brain stimulation (DBS) [2,3].

The intended user population includes trainees in universities, medical device developers, and regulatory scientists. The tool can facilitate in-silico safety testing and design optimization for medical devices.

Testing

VF1.0 is the first generation of models, originally developed for electromagnetic exposure evaluations. About 80 different tissues and organs were identified and segmented for each model [1]. The segmentation was carried out organ by organ or tissue by tissue. Although the image processing software significantly facilitated the segmentation process, the correct identification of tissues required 3D visualization of the organ shape. Several iterations per organ were necessary to achieve a satisfactory result. The angiographic image sets of the vessel trees supported the segmentation of the blood vessels of the two adult models. To test the segmentation quality, International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP) reference phantoms' organ masses were used. There is good agreement between the organ masses of the ICRP reference phantoms and the obtained models for most tissues and organs. Certain deviations can be attributed to the segmentation uncertainties—mainly of the digestive tract. Deviations of the masses of those tissues, which show up clearly in the MR images, are due to individual properties of the volunteers [1].

Limitations

Despite the high contrast and resolution of the MR images, certain compromises during the segmentation were inevitable. Although the outlines of most of the tissues in VF models could be constructed with an accuracy of 1 to 2 pixels of the original images, the limitations of the models are as follows.

- Blood vessels with a diameter of less than 2 mm were not included [1] (Recently the Virtual Population 3.0 became available [8]. Blood vessels with a diameter of less than 1 mm is available at the Virtual Population 3.0).
- Nerve tissues only include the spinal cord and the optic nerve [1] (the Virtual Population 3.0 includes initial sections of the spinal nerves (about 2 cm) as well as the sciatic and tibial nerves [8])
- Despite the administration of the anticholinergic agent to the adult volunteers, the imaging quality of the digestive tract was not sufficient for a complete segmentation. The intestinal ducts and the lumina could not be reconstructed completely; the pancreas could only be reconstructed for the male adult model [1].
- The cortex of the kidneys and the walls of the stomach and the gall bladder were indistinguishable from the medulla and the lumen, respectively. They were segmented using a fixed thickness of five pixels of the MR images [1].
- The salivary glands have not been segmented separately [1].
- Only small fractions of the diaphragm were visible in the images. It has therefore been reconstructed with the help of anatomical atlases [1].
- The bone marrow of the two female models has not been segmented for the entire body [8]. Since white and yellow marrow cannot be told apart in the MR images, the bone marrow has been segmented as yellow marrow in the male models.
- The periosteum has not been segmented separately for all models [8].
- The extrathoracic region has not been identified as a separate region [1].

The VF2.0 models are distributed as surface meshes in stereolithography (STL) format. Each tissue is

stored as a separate surface mesh, which is guaranteed to be closed, but may contain non-manifold edges or vertices. Note also that some software tools are unfortunately not able to deal with non-manifold surfaces.

Supporting Documentation

Tool websites:

[MIDA Model \(itis.swiss\)](#)

[DOI: 10.13099/ViP-MIDA-V1.0](#)

1. [MIDA: A Multimodal Imaging-Based Detailed Anatomical Model of the Human Head and Neck](#) Maria Ida Iacono, Esra Neufeld, Esther Akinngbe, Kelsey Bower, Johanna Wolf, Ioannis Oikonomidis, Deepika Sharma, Bryn Lloyd, Bertram Wilm, Michael Wyss, Klaas Pruessmann, Andras Jakab Nikos Makris, Ethan Cohen, Niels Kuster, Wolfgang Kainz, and Leonardo M. Angelone, in PLoS ONE 10(4): e0124126. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0124126, April 2015
2. [A computational model for bipolar deep brain stimulation of the subthalamic nucleus](#) Maria Ida Iacono, Esra Neufeld, Bonmassar Giorgio, Esther Akinngbe, Andras Jakab, Ethan Cohen, Niels Kuster, Wolfgang Kainz and Leonardo Angelone, in IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society, pp. 6258-61, 2014
3. [Simulation platform for coupled modeling of EM-induced neuronal dynamics and functionalized anatomical models](#) Neufeld Esra, Ioannis Oikonomidis, Maria Ida Iacono, Esther Akinngbe, Leonardo Angelone, Wolfgang Kainz and Niels Kuster, in 7th International IEEE EMBS Neural Engineering Conference, 2015

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Tool Reference

In addition to citing relevant publications please reference the use of this tool using DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8228899

For more information

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